

Flat Artificial Structure

FAS

Characteristics:

- **Type:** Man-made, artificial structure built entirely in space.
- **Timeframe for Construction (Year):** 10,000 - 100,000+
- **Radius:** 10,000 km
- **Surface Area:** Approximately 3.1×10^8 km² (or 3.1×10^{10} hectares)
- **(Potential) Hosted Population:** 6.2×10^{12} or (6.2 trillion people) - based on a density of 200 people per hectare.

Note: The numbers and data in this manuscript are approximations and purely theoretical.

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